

SYSTEM OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Xaydarov Muzaffar Urmanovich

*Graduate student of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology of the Asian
International University:*

Abstract: It is known that the production of young teachers and pedagogues is becoming one of the main requirements of the labor market of our country. In this thesis, basic and brief concepts for the development of socio-pedagogical competence of future teachers have been given.

Key words: Professional competence, Higher educational institutions and pedagogical lyceums, Teaching practices, Work with students, Learning experience

Main part: Professional competence and professional self-awareness is a lifelong process, a person chooses a profession from the stages of dreaming, trying, choosing and realizing them, then entering a profession, and then changing professions in the world. , changes his profession or specialty depending on the change in himself, the change in his attitude to work. Professional competence means complex integrated education, including a set of knowledge of professional importance. Skills and abilities, personal qualities, certain ways of thinking and a certain level of responsibility for one's actions are understood. The embodiment of perfection plays an important role in the image of a modern teacher. Developing the professional competence of today's teacher is to increase his daily ability and productivity of the work process. It is possible to train qualified specialists by studying and solving problems related to the formation of professional skills in work, forming professional training. The need to improve pedagogical and psychological knowledge and skills of future teachers is based on the growth of social demands placed on educational institutions and teachers. In the field of higher education, determination of the actual needs for education is carried out based on the determination of the level of their professional training, the aspects that meet the requirements, as well as the existing shortcomings and gaps. Based on this, it is appropriate to implement innovations. This leads to the development of pedagogical competence. Another important situation during training sessions is to organize the learning processes of students based on their needs and to focus on the personality of the student. These include methods of forming students' interest in learning, their sense of duty and responsibility in the educational process. Organization and development of cooperative work of subjects in the further improvement of

pedagogical processes, the effectiveness of developing their activity in the system of goals and tasks that are important to achieve, in every way depends on existing motives and motivation. The field of education is a social institution that reflects all the problems of society.

In general, the system of development of socio-pedagogical competence of future teachers may consist of the following elements:

✚ Higher educational institutions and pedagogical lyceums: Teachers increase their pedagogical knowledge by conducting training in higher educational institutions or pedagogical lyceums. In these institutions, teachers can strengthen their theoretical knowledge in practice, teach students theoretical knowledge and organize practical training.

✚ Teaching practices: Teachers develop their pedagogical competence by presenting themselves as products of teaching. These practices help teachers analyze the learning process, organize lessons, apply to students, and evaluate.

✚ Working with students: Future teachers develop their socio-pedagogical competences by working with students. It is important for teachers to communicate with students, help them meet the necessary requirements and master them.

✚ Learning experience: Teachers strengthen their socio-pedagogical competence by developing learning experience. This learning experience helps to increase practical knowledge through teaching, creating projects, conducting research and other pedagogical activities.

Conclusion: The system of development of socio-pedagogical competence of future teachers will help them to improve their pedagogical knowledge, organize practical training and strengthen the educational process. This system allows teachers to develop professionally and provide quality education to students.

References:

1. Second generation standards. Approximate program in physics. (Basic school).
2. Formation of universal educational activities in primary school: from idea to thought. /under. ed. A.G. Asmolova .—M.: Enlightenment, 2010
3. A.V. Fedotova . “The role of universal educational activities in the system of modern general education”.
4. Yakushina E.V. Getting ready for the lesson in the new state educational standards. Internet and education. 2012

5. BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNING KASBIY KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH 1Nasiba Sabirova, 2 Zumrad Masharipova 1Xorazm VPYMO‘MM "Tillarni o`qitish metodikasi" kafedrası mudiri, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent 2UrDU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi